

MEDIATION OF BRAND LOYALTY BETWEEN BRAND AWARENESS AND DESTINATION BRANDING GEOPARK LAKE TOBA

SRI RAHAYU¹ and MEGASARI GUSANDRA SARAGIH*²

^{1,2} Management of Study Program, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Medan, Indonesia.

*Email: megasariigusandrasaragih@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of brand awareness on the destination branding of the Lake Toba Geopark with brand loyalty as an intervening variable. The main problem in this study is the decline in the number of tourist visits to the Lake Toba Geopark, apart from being caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, but also due to issues of environmental destruction. The number of samples as many as 150 tourists, with a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling approach. This research uses path analysis method with AMOS 24.0. The results of the study found that brand awareness affects brand loyalty and destination branding Lake Toba Geopark. Brand loyalty affects destination branding Lake Toba Geopark. Brand loyalty mediates in partial mediation the influence of brand awareness on destination branding Lake Toba Geopark.

Keywords: brand awareness, brand loyalty, destination branding.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the largest countries in the world, reaching more than 5.1 million km² covering land and sea. It stretches from the eastern end of Papua to the western end of Sumatra for 3,977 miles. It has more than 17 thousand islands. Naturally, this country has extraordinary natural wealth. This is a potential for the tourism sector. Unfortunately, only Bali is already very global. Whereas Indonesia has other "Bali-Bali" which if managed seriously will be able to bring extraordinary income for the people of Indonesia. Herein lies the challenge.

Since 2016, the Government through the Ministry of Tourism has introduced the 10 New Bali program. This program is focused on 10 destinations such as Lake Toba in North Sumatra, Tanjung Kelayang Belitung, Borobudur Temple in Central Java, Labuan Bajo East Nusa Tenggara, Mandalika West Nusa Tenggara, Thousand Islands, Morotai North Maluku, Wakatobi Southeast Sulawesi, Bromo Tengger Semeru in East Java. And Tanjung Lesung in Banten. Recently, the Ministry of Tourism and the creative economy has focused on 5 locations called super priority destinations. The five are Lake Toba, Borobudur, Likupang, Mandalika and Labuan Bajo.

Toba Caldera or better known as Lake Toba was designated as a UNESCO Global Geopark at the 209th Session of the UNESCO Executive Council in Paris, France, Tuesday 2 July 2020. The Indonesian government succeeded in convincing the UN Agency for Education, Science and Culture that the Toba Caldera has geological links and high traditional heritage with local communities, especially in terms of culture and biodiversity. Lake Toba has an area of 1,130 km², with details of 87 km long and 27 km wide. Because of its size, Lake Toba (1,130 km²)

is included in the area of seven districts (Simalungun, Toba Samosir, North Tapanuli, Humbang Hasundutan, Dairi, Karo and Samosir).

Lake Toba holds a lot of potential for natural beauty, unique flora and fauna and a charming cultural diversity. However, it takes a mature strategy to make Lake Toba global. This is because the competition in the tourism sector is very tight. Many other countries also have natural beauty that is not inferior to Lake Toba. Therefore, a strong branding is needed for Lake Toba so that Lake Toba is easily recognized and easily remembered by tourists.

The application of a branding strategy in a city/place begins with the assumption that the individual understands the area as he understands the brand (Yananda & Salamah, 2014). How a place is perceived and imaged in people's minds is what matters. Therefore, the best way to influence perceptions and images about a place is believed to be the same way the business world tries to build perceptions and images about its products or companies, namely through branding (Kavaratzis & Ashworth, 2005).

Furthermore, according to Ashworth & Kavaratzis (2009), place branding is an idea to develop a place by creating its own uniqueness in that place, with the aim of finding differences with other places around it. Ashworth & Kavaratzis (2009) explain that in creating the uniqueness of a place, at least three things are needed: associations attached to places, buildings or landmarks that are typical of place markers and events that only occur in that place. Well, Lake Toba has these three things. Where the uniqueness of Lake Toba and the history behind the formation of Lake Toba become a branding destination that is not owned by other lakes in the world.

The management of destination branding has recently emerged as a prominent trend in modern tourism (Rather & Hollebeek, 2020; Tsaur et al., 2016). Resort branding is essential for a tourist destination to stand out from competitors and be recognized in the target market (Kim & Malek, 2017; Kumar & Kaushik, 2017; Najjar, 2018). Therefore, destination marketers can utilize destination branding as a technique to draw tourists and/or gain a competitive edge over other similar places (Berrozpe et al., 2019; Tsaur et al., 2016). A destination really needs a brand as a medium to communicate to consumers about the type or purpose of its product, and that is what distinguishes the product from other products (Morrison & Anderson, 2002). Destination Branding is a strategy on how to market the potential of an area (Situmorang, 2008).

Previous research stated that brand awareness and brand loyalty are important ingredients for the success of destination branding. Brand awareness plays an important role in building destination branding (Cai, 2002). The capacity of a potential customer to recognize or recall that a brand is a part of a specific product category is known as brand awareness (Rangkuti, 2009). To achieve destination branding success requires coordinated work on Presented Brand, Brand Awareness, Brand Meaning and Brand Equity with tourists and local residents (Emrizal, 2016). Brand awareness indicators include: Recall, Recognition, Purchase and Consumption (Soehadi, 2005).

Destination branding is thought to have the ability to alter perspectives and perceptions of a place or destination, including the ability to distinguish between a location and another location

that might be used as a destination (Soenaryo, 2013). Tourism academics and practitioners are aware of the importance of visitor brand loyalty and brand awareness, which are related aspects of brand equity (Huerta-Alvarez, Cambra-Fierro, & Fuentes-Blasco, 2020). For instance, Hsu and Chen (2018) showed that brand awareness is a crucial source of brand knowledge, a crucial stage of consumers' commitment to a particular brand, and that brand awareness is inextricably tied to brand loyalty. Brand awareness had a strong and advantageous impact on brand loyalty, according to studies by Xu et al. (2016) and Kim et al. (2018). There are a number of variables that can impact destination branding, including (Aaker, 1996): brand awareness, brand loyalty, brand image, perceived quality, brand associations, and property rights.

This research is important to do to find out how far the destination branding of the Lake Toba Geopark is so that it is expected to increase the number of tourist visits to the Lake Toba Geopark which is positively correlated with increasing the original income of the Toba Samosir Regency and for the creation of sustainable tourism development in the Lake Toba Geopark tourist area.

Problems and Goals

The main problem is the decline in the number of tourist visits to the Lake Toba Geopark, apart from being caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, but also due to issues of environmental destruction. This research is important to do to increase the number of tourist visits and local revenue of Toba Samosir Regency and for the sake of creating sustainable tourism development in the Lake Toba Geopark tourist area so that it can be enjoyed by future generations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Path Analysis Model is the data analysis method employed. Only visitors who have been to Lake Toba are eligible to participate as respondents, and a nonprobability sampling strategy with a selective sampling approach was used to carry out the sample technique. Depending on the analytical technique being utilized, the number of samples is decided. The number of pieces might range from 5 to 10 of the number of indicators, according to SEM. $15 \times 10 = 150$ respondents made up the study's total number of samples. Questionnaires on a scale from 1 to 5 were administered directly to 150 respondents who were visitors to Lake Toba as part of the data collection process. We investigate the level of significance of the association between variables using Ferdinand (2014) as a reference. The indirect influence will be examined in light of Baron & Kenny's assessment.

The full model in this study can be seen in Figure 1 below:

Fig 1: Research Full Model

By Equation:

$$Z = b_1X + Z_5 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$Y = b_2X + b_3Z + Z_6 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Description:

- Z = Brand Loyalty
- Y = Destination Branding
- X = Brand Awareness
- b₁ - b₃ = Coefficient Variable
- Z₅ - Z₆ = error term

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

If the stacking figure value for each item or marker is greater than 0.60, the variable pointer is said to be significant. Table 2 below displays the results of the CFA test for each variable:

Based on Table 1, it is known that all indicators have a CFA value > 0.60 so that the indicator is said to be valid and feasible to be tested at a later stage.

Table 1. CFA Test Result

Standardized Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Variable Indicator	Estimate	Cut of Value	Conclusion
X1 <--- BrandAwareness	,763	0,60	Valid
X2 <--- BrandAwareness	,744	0,60	Valid
X3 <--- BrandAwareness	,750	0,60	Valid
X4 <--- BrandAwareness	,774	0,60	Valid
Z1 <--- BrandLoyalty	,750	0,60	Valid
Z2 <--- BrandLoyalty	,771	0,60	Valid
Z3 <--- BrandLoyalty	,742	0,60	Valid
Z4 <--- BrandLoyalty	,720	0,60	Valid
Y1 <--- DestinationBranding	,807	0,60	Valid
Y2 <--- DestinationBranding	,792	0,60	Valid
Y3 <--- DestinationBranding	,777	0,60	Valid
Y4 <--- DestinationBranding	,757	0,60	Valid
Y5 <--- DestinationBranding	,807	0,60	Valid
Y6 <--- DestinationBranding	,768	0,60	Valid
Y7 <--- DestinationBranding	,824	0,60	Valid

b. Normality test

Table 2. Normality Test Result

Assessment of normality (Group number 1)

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
Y7	2,000	5,000	,238	1,191	-,536	-1,340
Y6	2,000	5,000	,048	,241	-,324	-,811
Y5	2,000	5,000	,111	,555	-,570	-1,424
Y4	2,000	5,000	,067	,334	-,384	-,959
Y3	2,000	5,000	,252	1,262	-,411	-1,028
Y2	2,000	5,000	,643	1,217	,057	,142
Y1	2,000	5,000	,014	,069	-,571	-1,427
Z4	2,000	5,000	,277	1,384	-,307	-,768
Z3	2,000	5,000	,289	1,446	-,491	-1,226
Z2	2,000	5,000	,113	,567	-,536	-1,341
Z1	2,000	5,000	,123	,614	-,457	-1,142
X4	2,000	5,000	,259	1,296	-,510	-1,274
X3	2,000	5,000	,001	,005	-,560	-1,400
X2	2,000	5,000	,164	,821	-,502	-1,255
X1	2,000	5,000	-,020	-,099	-,414	-1,035
Multivariate					-7,306	-1,981

There are no univariate values for the crucial ratio skewness esteem in Table 2 that are beyond the esteem range of 2.58. Additionally, since the multivariate basic proportion esteem of kurtosis is also within the range of 2.58, which equals -1,981, it may be inferred that both univariate and multivariate information are frequently communicated in this context.

Model Fit Test

The full model before being modified is done to see how far the basic model formed can meet the goodness of fit (GOF) criteria. Here are the results of the data processing:

Figure 2. Full Research Model before Modification

Based on Figure 2, it is known that not all the constructs used meet the GOF criteria. It can be seen from the GFI, AGFI and P-value values which are still bad. Because the GOF value still does not meet the criteria, the next step is to modify the model by connecting the error term suggested by the system.

Figure 3. Full Research Model after Modification

From Figure 3 it is detailed to Table 3 the following Goodness of Fit (GOF) criteria:

Table 3. Criteria GOF Full Model

Goodness Of Fit Index	Expected Value	Result Value	Conclusion
χ^2 C-square Statistics	Diharapkan kecil	128,210	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,900	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,855	Marginal
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,969	Good
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,976	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,060	Good
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	1,545	Good
P-Value	$\geq 0,05$	0,073	Good

With the exception of the AGFI score, which still marginal but approaching good, Table 3 shows that the development used to create this inquiry show has met the GOF standards. The p-value, which is already significant and higher than 0.05 and is 0.073, demonstrates the significance of the study.

Discussion

To see how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable, it is shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4. The Effect of Dependent Variables on Independent Variables

Effect Between Variables	Std. Estimate	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
BrandLoyalty <--- BrandAwareness	,683	,723	,096	7,549	***
DestinationBranding <--- BrandAwareness	,516	,567	,080	7,126	***
DestinationBranding <--- BrandLoyalty	,493	,571	,080	7,104	***

Based on Table 4, the following equation can be generated:

Equation I: $Z = b1X + Z6$

$$Z = 0,683 X$$

Equation II: $Y = b2X + b3Z + Z7$

$$Y = 0,516 X + 0,493 Z$$

From Table 4, the findings in this study can be described, namely:

a. Effect of brand awareness on brand loyalty

With a ranking coefficient of the normalized regression of 0.683 (68,3%), the probability or meaning of 0.0001 (significant), and the value of CR of 7,548, the relationship between brand awareness and brand loyalty is significant. In other words, brand loyalty among visitors to the Lake Toba Geopark is influenced by brand awareness.

b. Effect of brand awareness on destination branding

With an estimated standardized regression weight coefficient of 0.683 (68,3%), the probability or significance value of 0.0001 (significant), and the C.R value of 7,126, the relationship between brand awareness and destination branding is substantial. In other words, destination branding is significantly impacted by brand awareness. Toba Lake Geopark.

c. Effect of brand loyalty on destination branding

With an estimated standardized regression weight coefficient of 0.493 (49,3%), the probability or significance value of 0.0001 (significant), and the C.R value of 7,104, brand loyalty has a positive and substantial impact on destination branding. In other words, Lake Toba Geopark's destination branding is significantly impacted by brand loyalty.

d. Mediation Effect Analysis (Intervening)

This study follows the opinion of Baron & Kenny (1986) for its mediating effect:

Figure 4: Sobel Test Results

Details can be found in Baron and Kenny (1986), Sobel (1982), Goodman (1960), and MacKinnon, Warsi, and Dwyer (1995). Insert the *a*, *b*, *s_a*, and *s_b* into the cells below and this program will calculate the critical ratio as a test of whether the indirect effect of the IV on the DV via the mediator is significantly different from zero.

	Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
<i>a</i>	0.683	Sobel test:	4.65805892	0.07228741	0.00000319
<i>b</i>	0.493	Aroian test:	4.63199051	0.07269423	0.00000362
<i>s_a</i>	0.096	Goodman test:	4.68457247	0.07187828	0.00000281
<i>s_b</i>	0.080	Reset all	Calculate		

Based on Figure 4, it was found that the probability of path -a (0.0001) and path -b (0.0001) was significant, -c (0.0001) was significant, and path -c' (0.000003) was significant. It can be concluded that brand loyalty partial mediates the effect of of brand awareness on destination branding Lake Toba Geopark. This implies that to increase the destination branding of Lake Toba Geopark, it can be done by using the brand loyalty of tourists.

CONCLUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis, several conclusions can be drawn as follows: 1) Brand awareness affects brand loyalty of tourists at the Lake Toba Geopark.; 2) Brand awareness has a significant effect on destination branding Lake Toba Geopark; 3) Brand loyalty has a significant effect on destination branding Lake Toba Geopark; 4) Brand loyalty partial mediates the effect of of brand awareness on destination branding Lake Toba Geopark.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. A. Measuring brand equity across products and markets. *California Management Review*, 38(3), 102-120. 1996.
- Ashworth, G, and M. Kavaratzis. (2009). "Beyond the Logo: Brand Management for Cities". *Brand Management*, 16 (8): 520-531.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. 1986. The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51, 1173-1182.
- Berrozpe, A., Campo, S., & Yague, M. J. (2019). Am I Ibiza? Measuring brand identification in the tourism context. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 11, 240–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2018.04.005>.
- Cai, L. A. (2002). Cooperative branding for rural destinations. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 29(3), 720–742.
- Emrizal. Destination Branding dalam Strategi Pemasaran Destinasi (Sebuah Tinjauan Teoritis). *Polibisnis*, Volume 8 No.2 Oktober 2016 ISSN 1858– 37171. 2016.
- Ferdinand, Augusty. 2014. *Metode Penelitian Manajemen*, Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Ghozali, Imam. 2013. *Konsep dan Aplikasi dengan Progran AMOS 21.0*. Cetakan ke 4, Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Hsu, C., & Chen, M. (2018). How does gamification improve user experience? An empirical investigation on the antecedences and consequences of user experience and its mediating role. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 132, 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.01.023>.
- Huerta-Alvarez, R., Cambra-Fierro, J., & Fuentes-Blasco, M. (2020). The interplay between social media communication, brand equity and brand engagement in tourist destinations: An analysis in an emerging economy. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 16, 100413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2020.100413>.
- Keller, K. L. (2013). *Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity*, (4th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc.
- Kavaratzis, M. and Ashworth, G.J. (2005), "City branding: an effective assertion of identity or a transitory marketing trick?" *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, Vol. 96 No. 5, pp. 506-14.
- Kim, S., Choe, J., & Petrick, J. (2018). The effect of celebrity on brand awareness, perceived quality, brand image, brand loyalty, and destination attachment to a literary festival. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 9, 320–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2018.03.006>.
- Kim, W., & Malek, K. (2017). Effects of self-congruity and destination image on destination loyalty: The role of cultural differences. *Anatolia. An International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 28(1), 1–13. doi: 10.1080/13032917.2016.1239209.
- Kumar, V., & Kaushik, A. K. (2017). Achieving destination advocacy and destination loyalty through destination brand identification. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 34(9), 1247–1260. doi: 10.1080/10548408.2017.1331871.
- Morrison, A., & Anderson, D. (2002). Destination branding. Retrieved from <http://www.macvb.org/intranet/presentation/DestinationBrandingLOzarks6-10-02.ppt>.
- Najar, A. H. (2018). Recovery marketing activities (RMA's): A tool to manage destination in conflict situation research literature review. *South Asian Journal of Tourism and Heritage*, 11(1), 21–32. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324773552_Recovery_Marketing_Activities_RMA's_A_Tool_to_Manage_Destination_in_Conflict_Situation-Research_Literature_Review/references.

- Rangkuti, Freddy. Strategi Promosi yang Kreatif dan Analisis Kasus Integrated Marketing Communication. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama. 2009.
- Rather, R. A., & Hollebeck, L. D. (2020). Experiential marketing for tourism destinations. In Saurabh Kumar Dixited (ed.), *the routledge handbook of tourism experience management and marketing*. Routledge Publications.
- Situmorang, S. H. (2008). Destination Brand: Membangun Keunggulan Bersaing Daerah. *Wahana Hijau Jurnal Perencanaan & Pengembangan Wilayah*, 4(2), 79–86.
- Soehadi, Agus W. *Effective Branding*. Bandung: PT. Mizan Pustaka. 2005.
- Soenaryo, Bambang. *Kebijakan pembangunan Destinasi Pariwisata*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media. 2013.
- Tsaur, S. H., Yen, C. H., & Yan, Y. T. (2016). Destination brand identity: Scale development and validation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 21(12), 1310–1323. doi: 10.1080/10941665.2016.1156003.
- Xu, F., Tian, F., Buhalis, D., Weber, J., & Zhang, H. (2016). Tourists as mobile gamers: Gamification for tourism marketing. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 33(8), 1124–1142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2015.1093999>.
- Yananda, M.Rahmat, dan Salamah, Umami. (2014), *Branding Tempat: Membangun Kota, Kabupaten, dan Provinsi Berbasis Identitas, Makna Informasi*, Jakarta.